

Recycling of Wasted Printed Circuit Boards in Near-critical Water and the Effects of Reaction Conditions on Decomposition Rate

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Abstract:

Printed circuit boards (PCB) from waste computers were decomposed in water at a near-critical condition in a non-stirring tubular reactor, for the purpose of separating and recycling the organic and metallic materials and glass fibers. Experiments were devised in order to identify some significant process parameters that affect the decomposition rate of PCBs, including temperature, time, sample size and catalyst concentration.

Keywords: Printed circuit board; Recycling; Near-critical water; Decomposition rate

1. Introduction

With the rapid development of electronic information industry, the upgrading of electronic products is accelerated, meanwhile produced vast quantities of electronic waste (E-waste). The European Commission's Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive has provided the official definition of E-waste, and appeared all its member states to reuse, recycle and recover all WEEE rather than simply disposing of it in landfill site [1]. PCBs are usually made up of thermoplastic with contents of flame retardants like bromide and antimony, glass fibers, and a variety of metal [2]. Metal contained in PCBs includes Cu, Fe, Al, Zn, Pb, and noble metals such as Au, Ag, Pt and Pd [3]. The metal grades of Cu, Au, Ag, Pt and Pd in PCBs are much higher than the ore grades of nature minerals, making the recycling value of waste PCBs extremely high [4]. Resin and glass fibers in waste PCBs also have considerable value to recycle.

However, waste PCB recycling is particularly problematic because of PCB's heterogeneous mix of organic material, metal and glass fibers. A series of certain process parameters is difficult to identify. Traditional recycling methods, such as combustion or washing in strong oxidizer [5], were very inefficient and produced toxic gases and effluent. Currently, waste PCBs are either incinerated, leading to the formation of toxic brominated compounds, or sent to landfill, leading to toxic compounds and heavy metals leaching into soil[6].

This paper presents findings of an investigation into waste PCBs recycling using near-critical water. The effect of reaction temperature, reaction time, and sample size were investigated, as well as the potential of catalysts like acids and alkalis to improve the process efficiency.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material

Printed circuit boards were removed mainly from computer motherboards. Larger sized, easily recyclable components were dismantled beforehand. The boards were then broken into pieces that were 2-4 cm². All circuit boards selected were multi-layer FR-4 copper clad laminate.

2.2. Reactor

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A non-stirring tubular reactor was used for each experiments, which was 150mm in length and 35mm in diameter. The reactor was fixed into a salt bath furnace, which was controlled by a programmable temperature controller.

2.3. Gas chromatography / mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

The decomposed product of resin in residual liquid was analyzed with GC-MS, using a HP-6890GC (AGILENT, USA) equipped with a mass spectrometer HP-5MS.

2.4. Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Residual glass fiber cloth and unreacted PCB sample were analyzed using SEM to identify the condition of glass fibers as well as visual signs of residual resin impurities.

3. Results and discussion

The experiments were divided into several parts to study the influence of different parameters on the decomposition rate (i.e. the yield of eliminated resin, wt. %) separately. Reaction time, temperature, sample size, and catalyst type (HCl, NaOH, Na₂CO₃ and NaCl) were selected as controlled variables. To identify the average proportion of resin in the PCBs, several randomly selected samples were reacted in an extreme condition (Listed in Table 1). Five samples were reacted at 633K for 180min and the weight loss were between 38.8% and 41.7%. One sample was reacted at same temperature for double time as long and the weight dropped 40.5%, which wasn't more than the former five samples. This result proved that resin in PCBs were completely degraded after reacted at 633K for 180min and the average proportion of resin in PCBs is

Table 1 Decomposition experiments in extreme conditions

No.	Temperature (K)	Time (min)	Sample size(cm ²)	Solvent volume(mL)	PCB/solvent ratio(g/mL)	Pressure (MPa)	Weight loss (wt. %)
1	633	180	1.8×2.1	13.5	0.1	17.2	39.2
2	633	180	1.9×2.1	13.9	0.1	17.0	41.7
3	633	180	2.0×2.0	13.8	0.1	16.9	38.8
4	633	180	1.8×1.6	10.0	0.1	13.6	40.9
5	633	180	1.9×1.7	11.0	0.1	14.0	40.8
6	633	360	2.0×2.0	12.6	0.1	14.5	40.5

approximate 39-42%. And the decomposition rate(i.e. yield of eliminated resin) can be calculated through formula below:

$$\text{Decomposition rate(\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{weight of sample} - \text{weight of solid residue}}{\text{weight of resin in sample}} \right) \times 100\%$$

$$\approx \left(\frac{\text{weight of sample} - \text{weight of solid residue}}{\text{weight of sample} \times \text{average proportion of resin}} \right) \times 100\%$$

3.1. The effect of reaction time on decomposition rate

In this section, reaction time was selected as controlled variable while all other factors were kept at their average values in order to study the effect of time. The results are listed in Table 2. Decomposition rate increases from 0.8% to 77.2% when reaction time is increased from 45min to

150min. The decomposition rate is very low when reaction time is below 60min but increases rapidly when reaction time is above 60min. With reaction time increasing, the solid residue changed from hard and inseparable, to very soft and completely separated.

Table 2 Results of time controlled decomposition experiments

No.	Temperature (K)	Time ^a (min)	Sample size(cm ²)	Solvent volume ^b (mL)	Pressure (MPa)	Decomposition Rate (%)
1	553	45	2.0×1.8	10	4.0	0.8
2	553	60	2.1×2.0	10	4.0	18.3
3	553	75	2.1×1.8	10	4.0	49.8
4	553	90	2.3×1.7	10	4.0	48.4
5	553	105	2.1×1.9	10	4.0	52.0
6	553	120	2.0×2.0	10	4.0	60.0
7	553	150	2.3×2.0	10	4.0	77.2

a time to reach the temperature and pressure in stationary state: 10min. approx.

b volume of water, placed into the reactor prior operation.

3.2. The effect of temperature on decomposition rate

In this section, temperature is selected as controlled variable, ranging from 513K to 633K. Results of this section are listed in Table 3. When temperature is low, the weight of sample increased. Same results came out from repeating experiments. We conjectured that some contents were oxidized and caused the weight increasing because actions were not performed in a oxygen-free condition for the limitation of equipment. The decomposition rate rose from 7.9% at 543K to 89.3% at 623K and increased quite rapidly between 543K and 563K. However, when temperature is higher than 573K, the decomposition rate didn't increase obviously. What cannot be ignored is that, when temperature is higher than 613K, residues, especially glass fiber cloth, become very friable. The mechanical properties of recycled glass fibers might be affected.

Table 3 Results of temperature controlled decomposition experiments

No.	Temperature (K)	Time (min)	Sample size(cm ²)	Solvent volume(mL)	Pressure (MPa)	Decomposition Rate(%)
1	533	90	2.2×1.5	10	4.0	-0.55 ^a
2	543	90	2.4×1.5	10	3.8	7.9
3	553	90	2.2×1.7	10	4.7	48.4
4	563	90	2.0×1.7	10	4.7	75.4
5	573	90	2.3×1.5	10	6.0	74.4
6	583	90	2.2×1.7	10	8.0	70.3
7	593	90	2.1×1.8	10	8.5	70.4
8	603	90	2.1×1.8	10	9.5	70.7
9	613	90	2.2×1.8	10	11.8	73.1
10	623	90	2.0×1.9	10	12.0	89.3

a “-” means the weight of sample increased after reaction.

The effect of sample size on decomposition rate

In this section, samples were broken into pieces of different sizes (with same total area) and reacted. Other factors are controlled at the same. Results are listed in Table 4.

Table 4 Results of sample size controlled decomposition experiments

No.	Temperature (K)	Time (min)	Sample size(cm ²)	Pieces	Pressure (MPa)	Decomposition rate(%)
1	573	60	2.0×2.0	1	6.0	64.6
2	573	60	1.0×1.0	4	6.0	77.3
3	573	60	1.0×0.5	8	6.0	88.3
4	573	60	0.5×0.5	16	6.0	91.9

Decomposition rate increased significantly when sample was broken into smaller pieces, rising from 64.6% to 91.9%. Obviously crushing sample into small pieces can accelerate decomposition and promote the recycling efficiency to a new level.

3.3. The effect of catalyst on decomposition rate

In this section, HCl, NaOH and Na₂CO₃ were selected as different types of catalysts and performed separately in same conditions. A blank controller experiment was also performed. All experiments were performed at the condition of 573K for 60min; sample size was 2×2 cm² and solvent volume was 10mL. The weight of catalyst was 0.02g. The results are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Results of catalysts added decomposition experiments

No.	Temperature (K)	Time (min)	Sample size(cm ²)	Solvent volume (mL)	Catalyst	Pressure (MPa)	Decomposition rate(%)
1	573	60	2×2	10	Blank	6.0	64.6
2	573	60	2×2	10	HCl	6.0	98.5
3	573	60	2×2	10	NaOH	6.0	65.0
4	573	60	2×2	10	Na ₂ CO ₃	6.0	69.9

Acid's strong effect on decomposition was showed in these results. The decomposition rate increased from 64.6% in blank groups to 98.5% in HCl added groups. Alkalis also improved the efficiency of decomposition, rose decomposition rate up to nearly 70%. But weak bases like Na₂CO₃ are more effective than strong bases like NaOH.

3.4. Results of GC-MS analysis

The decomposed liquid product from experiment performed at 563K, 4.7MPa, reaction time 150min and solvent volume 10mL was selected to be analyzed. The products in residual water were extracted by ethyl acetate, and be detected. Fig. 2 is the gas chromatography of the products. The results of qualitative and quantitative analysis are in Table 6. Only constituents of which content is high and the similarity is over 60% were listed. It can be seen from Table 6 that most of the products are phenolic compounds.

Fig. 1 Gas chromatography of decomposed product reacted at 563K, 4.7MPa.

Table 6 Results of GC-MS analysis of decomposed products reacted at 563K, 4.7MPa..

Peak number	Retention time (min)	Name	Molecular formula	Structural formula	Molecular mass(m/z)	Area%
1	4.02	phenol	C ₆ H ₆ O		94	64.71
2	7.21	3-isopropylphenol	C ₉ H ₁₂ O		136	8.41
3	8.23	3-isopropenylphenol	C ₉ H ₁₀ O		134	9.69
4	9.16	3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-3-ol	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂		150	3.03
5	10.69	1-phenoxypropanediol	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₃		168	3.43
6	17.88	bisphenol A	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂		228	5.68

3.5. Results of SEM analysis

The glass fiber reclaimed from experiments performed at 573K, 6MPa and 593K, 8MPa (both reaction time 150min and solvent volume 10mL) were analyzed by SEM (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). Some resin impurities are still remaining on the surface of glass fiber after 573K near-critical water treatment (Fig. 2 with a 74.4% decomposition rate). But these residual resin impurities are much less observed in Fig. 3, which sample was reacted at 593K, 8MPa with a decomposition rate of 95.7%. It can be observed on 100× magnified micrographs that the arrangement of fibers is tight and tidy. On 2000× magnified micrographs, fiber surface is very smooth without trace of damaged. So the effect of thermal hydrolyzing treatment on the mechanical properties of glass fibers is insignificant. Immediately re-use of these reclaimed fibers would be allowed through thermal hydrolysis recycling.

Fig. 2 SEM micrograph of reclaimed glass fiber reacted at 573K, 6MPa, at 100× (left) and 2000× (right).

Fig. 3 SEM micrograph of reclaimed glass fiber reacted at 593K, 8MPa, at 100× (left) and 2000× (right).

4. Conclusion

Printed circuit boards removed from computer were degraded in near-critical water condition for temperature ranging from 513K to 633K, pressure from 3MPa to 17MPa, reaction time from 30min to 180min. The experiments performed between 553K and 623K for 90min provided resin decomposition rates from 48.4% (at 553K) to 89.3% (at 623K), showing that decomposition rates increase with temperature. The decomposition rate was further increased when sample was broken into small pieces prior operation, up to 91.9% just at a temperature of 573K.

The use of strong acids, such as HCl, catalyzed the decomposition kinetics, raising the rate up to 98.5% in experiments of 573K, 6MPa and 60min. Alkalis, such as NaOH and Na₂CO₃, also have a function of catalyst, but not so effective as acids. In addition, weak bases like Na₂CO₃ are more effective than strong bases, according to experiments results.

Through SEM analysis, it can be observed that reclaimed glass fibers were hardly damaged in this near-critical water condition. For solid residues from experiments with a decomposition rate higher than 70%, glass fiber clothes and metal can be separated easily. Furthermore, the reaction temperature of near-critical water is much lower than incineration and pyrolysis, as well as energy consumption. This concept is definitely worth pursuing as an environmental friendly, low energy consumption, and high-producing recycling method for PCBs.

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References

- [1] J.E. Hoffmann, Recovering precious metals from electronic scrap, *JOM*, 44 (1992) 43-48.
- [2] J.R. Cui, E. Forssberg, Mechanical recycling of waste electric and electronic equipment: a review, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, B99 (2003) 243-263.
- [3] Menad N., Björkman B., Allain E. G., Combustion of plastics contained in electric and electronic scrap, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 24(1998)65- 85.
- [4] Ehner T., Integrated recycling of non-ferrous metal at Boliden Ltd., *IEEE International Symposium on Electronics & the Environment*, (1998) 42-47.
- [5] Jia Li, Hongzhou Lu, Jie Guo, Zhenming Xu, Yaohe Zhou, *Recycle Technology for Recovering Resources and Products from Waste Printed Circuit Boards*, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 41 (2007) 1995-2000.
- [6] William J. Hall, Paul T. Williams, Separation and recovery of materials from scrap printed circuit boards, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 51(2007)691 - 709